

Observational Study

Prospective Observational Study of Scrub Typhus: It's Clinical Manifestations and Complications

Ajay V Daphale, Sagar Idhol*

Author affiliations

Department of Medicine, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Memorial Medical College (P.D.M.M.C.), Amravati, Maharashtra, India

Address reprint requests to

Dr Sagar Idhol
Department of Medicine, Dr. P.D.M.M.C. Amravati, Maharashtra, India
Email: sagaridhol@gmail.com

Abstract:

Objective To identify various complications along with the clinical manifestations related to Scrub Typhus.

Methods A prospective study based on the examination of the patients in the category of acute febrile illness of the age 8 years and above. The study was conducted in the Dr PDMMC hospital located in Amravati, Maharashtra, India. The diagnosis was made using clinical as well as serological data.

Results Total 50 patients were diagnosed with scrub typhus, with a greater number of males suffering from the disease as compared to the females. The major population of the patients, i.e., 42.12%, belonged to the age group of 18 to 30 years. Fever accompanied by headaches was considered the most common symptom which was present in almost 94.5% of the patients. Further, the most common complication was observed to be multiple organ failure in around 16.30% of the patients.

Conclusion The study discloses various clinical manifestations and complications that are caused due to the microorganism *Orientia tsutsugamushi* in the state of Maharashtra. The varied presentations and high mortality require a high index of suspicion. The study was conducted for four months from month of June to September, 2018.

Key words: Scrub Typhus, Complications, Clinical Features, Treatment.

INTRODUCTION

Scrub Typhus is caused by the microorganism *Orientia tsutsugamushi*. Due to this, the disease is also known as tsutsugamushi disease. "Typos" a Greek word is the origin of "Typhus", where Typos meaning high fever with state of unconsciousness. The disease is dates back to 1536, reported primarily by Girolamo Cardano, who was a physician of Italian origin. In India, this disease was first administered at the time of independence in the areas of the Assam-Burma border. This disease is said to occur in the areas specified as the "*Tsutsugamushi Triangle*"^[1]. In this area Japan is to the East, the west side covered by Afghanistan and the Middle-East region and in between lies the areas of Pacific islands, North Australia, Indonesia along with South-East Asia.

The disease is said to be a zoonotic disease caused by the rodents, rabbits and marsupials. It can also be transmitted through infected needles and blood transfusions. However, it is not a communicable disease^[2]. The microorganism can only be transmitted to the human body at the time it is in the form of chiggers (larva). Thus, wild rats prove to be the best hosts for the mite to get transmitted them to the human body^[3]. In spite, being a disease leading to febrile illness, Scrub Typhus remains undetected due to the lack of adequate information and also the lack of availability of any particular diagnostic tests. As the patients suffering from the disease show symptoms similar to malaria, typhoid and leptospirosis, after ruling out these diseases are able to identify the patient to be suffering from Scrub Typhus^[4].

As per a study conducted by Siddique *et al.*, (2016)^[5] it was made clear that the doctor needs to know the areas that would preferably can become the sites of eschars from the point of view of the patient likely to be infected by Scrub Typhus. However, the author also suggests that the absence of eschars does not serve as the proof of ruling out the possibility of the patient being infected from the disease. Thus, it is suggested in the study that scrub typhus is associated with a higher rate of mortality and a high index of suspicion would only be helpful in reducing the rate of mortality through this disease. Another study by Mahajan *et al.*, (2006)^[6] suggested that "Weil-Felix" test would prove to be helpful in the diagnosis for the patients being infected by scrub typhus. Further, the author added that there is lack of any specific diagnostic test for the disease in India and thus if interpreted the test correctly, would be, to some extent, helpful in managing the disease in a better manner. The common complications of the disease include hepatitis, kidney injury, myocarditis, meningoencephalitis and septic shock^[7].

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

To identify various complications along with the clinical manifestations related to Scrub Typhus.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A prospective study based on the examination of the patients in the category of acute febrile illness of the age 18 years and above. The study was conducted in the department of general medicine, Dr PDMMC hospital, Amravati, India.

INCLUSION CRITERIA

- All the patients that were admitted in the department of general medicine with a diagnosis of scrub typhus.
- Belonged to the age of 18 years and above.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

- Patients that were diagnosed with some other infections as well.
- Those patients showing other adjuvant conditions like chronic liver disease, renal failure, or neoplastic disease.

Diagnosis of scrub typhus has been made if a patient falls in any of the following three groups:

- **Group A:** Acute febrile illness with eschar specific for scrub typhus plus serological test positive for scrub (in Weil-Felix test titre for OXK more or equal to 1:160 or immunochromatographic card test (IgM, IgG and IgA) positive for scrub typhus).
- **Group B:** Acute febrile illness + Weil-Felix test titre for OXK more than or equal to 1:320.
- **Group C:** Acute febrile illness highly suspicious of scrub typhus plus Weil-Felix test titre for OXK equal to 1:160 or immunochromatographic card test (IgM, IgG and IgA) positive for scrub typhus plus response to doxycycline.

All patients diagnosed to have scrub typhus or those with strong clinical suspicion of scrub typhus were treated with doxycycline in the dose of 100 mg twice daily PO for 10 days unless it is contraindicated like pregnancy. In cases where doxycycline was not used

azithromycin in a dose of 500 mg once daily for 5 days given. As per indication other supportive measures were given like haemodialysis, mechanical ventilation, blood transfusion, inotropic agent etc.

RESULT AND OBSERVATION

In the present study, 50 patients were diagnosed to be infected by scrub typhus.

Table 1 shows that out of 50 patients, 58% (N = 29) were male and 42% (N = 21) were female. Further, majority of the patients were aged between 18 and 40 years.

Table 1 Age and sex distribution.

Age Group	18-30 years	31-40 years	41-50 years	51-60 years	>60 years
Male	11(22%)	9(18%)	5(10%)	2(4%)	2(4%)
Female	8(16%)	6(12%)	5(10%)	1(17.24%)	1(17.24%)
Total	19(38%)	15(30%)	10(20%)	3(6%)	3(6%)

Table 2 shows that major signs and symptoms of scrub typhus are fever, headache, cough, dyspnea, etc.

Table 1 Signs and symptoms at presentation and investigation findings.

Signs and symptoms	n-(%)	Investigation	N (%)
Fever	48(96%)	Haemoglobin less than 11 gm/dl	16(36%)
Headache	46(92%)	Leucocytosis (> 11,000/cumm)	13(26%)
Cough	25(50%)	Leucopenia (< 4,000/cumm)	2(4%)
Dyspnoea	16(32%)	Platelet (less than or equal to 1,50,000/cumm)	16(32%)
Lymphadenopathy	Cervical 12(24%)	Platelet count less than 80,000/cumm	6(12%)
	Inguinal 10(20%)	Hyperbilirubinaemia (> 1 mg/dl)	31(62%)
	Auxiliary 1(2%)	Sr Bilirubin (> 3 mg/dl)	16(32%)
	Generalized 4(8%)	SGOT (> 50 U/L)	42(84%)
Eschar	Inguinal 6(12%)	SGOT (> 150 IU/L)	24(48%)
	Lower limb 6(12%)	SGPT (50 U/L)	38(76%)
	Trunk 2(4%)	SGPT (> 150 IU/L)	9(18%)
	Axilla 1(2%)	ALKP (> 300 IU/L)	16(32%)

Rash	1(2%)	Sr creatinine (> 1.6 mg/dl)	13(26%)
Jaundice	8 (16%)		
Oliguria	5(10%)		
Altered sensorium	9(18%)		
Neck rigidity	4(8%)		
Bleeding	Epistaxis 1(2%)		
	Haemoptysis 3(6%)		
Hepatomegaly	11(22%)		
Splenomegaly	8(16%)		

Table 2 Complications and mortality.

Complications	No (%)
Hepatitis	8(16%)
Acute renal failure	7(14%)
Pancreatitis	1(2%)
ARDS	6(12%)
MODS	8(16%)
Meningoencephalitis	5(8%)
Mortality	5(8%)

Haemoglobin less than 11 gm/dl was present in 16(36%), leucocytosis in 13(26%), leucopenia in 2(4%), platelet count less than 80,000/cumm in 6(12%) number of patients. Deranged liver function was present in 42(84%) and deranged renal function in 11(22%) of patients respectively. Associated complications found were hepatitis in 8(16%) and acute renal failure in 7(14%) (These do not include patients having MODS), others include pancreatitis, ARDS, MODS and meningoencephalitis as shown in **Table 3**. Five patients expired with a mortality rate of 8% in the present study.

DISCUSSION

Scrub typhus is a disease spread by bacteria of the rickettsiaceae family. the disease mainly spreads through carriers that roam around the breeding grounds of the mites. as it is only possible for human beings to be exposed to mites only in the stage when it is a chigger or when it is a larva. thus, it travels through a host, i.e. rodents, etc. a wide range of studies has shown

that there is a lack of any particular diagnostic test; thus a high index of suspicion is the only possible solution for diagnosis^[8].

As per the study conducted by Siddique *et al.*, (2016)^[5] it was made clear that the doctor needs to know the areas that would preferably can become the sites of eschars from the point of view of the patient likely to be infected by scrub typhus. however, the author also suggests that the absence of eschars does not serve as the proof of ruling out the possibility of the patient being infected from the disease. thus, it is suggested in the study that scrub typhus is associated with a higher rate of mortality and a high index of suspicion would only be helpful in reducing the rate of mortality through this disease. in the present study also a very low percentage of patients showed eschars as a sign or a symptom of the disease. further, in the study mentioned above, it was also seen that empirical therapy with doxycycline and macrolides is the treatment of choice for scrub typhus. as per our study, similar dosages have been used for the patients.

Furthermore, a study conducted by Varghese, *et al.*, (2014)^[9] it was observed that fever (100%), headache (46%), cough (38%) and altered sensorium (26%) were found. the results in the current study were very much similar to this study as fever (96%), headache (92%), cough (50%) and altered sensorium (18%) were found in the patients. the study also revealed that scrub typhus could manifest with potentially life-threatening complications such as lung injury, shock, and meningoencephalitis and our study also suggested similar results.

CONCLUSION

The present study clearly administered various manifestations complications related to Scrub Typhus. The study reveals fever, headache, cough and altered sensorium to be the most important symptoms of the disease. Whereas, hepatitis and renal failure as the major complications of the disease ultimately leading to death in a majority of the patients. It was also found that the disease majorly affects the masses due to the lack of proper diagnosis and the availability of diagnosis. The study also shows the response of treatment with Doxycycline.

REFERENCES

1. Jamil Md. *et al.* Clinical Manifestations and Complications of Scrub Typhus: A Hospital Based Study from North Eastern India. *J Assoc Physicians India* 2014; 62:19-23.
2. Atul Kulkarni, Sunil Vaidya, Pramod Kulkarni, L.H.Bidri, Sandesh Padwal. Rickettsial disease - An Experience: *Pediatr Infect Dis J* 2009;1:118-126.
3. Pothukuchi Venkata Krishna, Shaik Ahmed, Katreddy Venkata Narsimha Reddy A case report of scrub typhus: *J Dr NTR Univ Health Sci* 2015;4(1):47-49.
4. Parul Sinha, Sweta Gupta, Romika Dawra, Puneet Rijhawan Recent outbreak of Scrub Typhus in North Western part of India: *Indian J Med Microbiol* 2014;32(3):247-250.
5. Siddique SG, Wyawahare AS, Bhalchandra MH, Mishra JK. A Case Report of Scrub Typhus with Multiorgan Dysfunction from Aurangabad Maharashtra. *Int J Health Sci Res* 2016; 6(5):416-19.
6. Mahajan SK, Kashyap R, Kanga A, Sharma V, Prasher BS, Pal LS. Relevance of Weil-Felix test in diagnosis of scrub typhus in India. *J Assoc Physicians India* 2006; 54:619-21.
7. Kedareshwar P.S, Narvencar, Savio Rodrigues, Ramnath P, Nevrekar, Lydia Dias, Amit Dias, Marina Vaz & E.Gomes-Scrub typhus in patients reporting with acute febrile illness at a tertiary health care institution in Goa. *Indian J Med Res* 2012;1020-1024.
8. David H Walker, Thomas Marrie, J. Stephen Dumler In *Harrisons Principles of internal medicine*. 19th edition Kasper, Fauci, Hauser, Longo, Jameson, Loscalzo, editors United States of America McGraw-Hill publishers. 2015; 1159.
9. Varghese GM, *et al.* Clinical profile and improving mortality trend of scrub typhus in South India. *Int J Infect Dis* 2014;23:39-43.

Article citation:

Ajay V Daphale, Sagar Idhol. Prospective observational study of scrub typhus: It's clinical manifestations and complications. *J Med Res Prac.* 2019;08(02):16-21. Available at <http://www.jmrp.info/index.php/jmrp>

Disclaimer:- Any views expressed in this paper are those of the authors and do not reflect the official policy or position of the Department of Defense.

Source of support: None